

Personalized cardiac computational models: from clinical data to simulation of infarct-related ventricular tachycardia

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13 remodeling (ER), fibrosis, slow conducting channel (SCC), computational simulation, radiofrequency
14 ablation (RFA)

15

16 **Abstract**

17 In the chronic stage of myocardial infarction, a significant number of patients develop life-threatening
18 ventricular tachycardias (VT) due to the arrhythmogenic nature of the remodeled myocardium.
19 Radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is a common procedure to isolate reentry pathways across the infarct
20 scar that are responsible for VT. Unfortunately, this strategy show relatively low success rates; up to
21 50% of patients experience recurrent VT after the procedure. In the last decade, intensive research in
22 the field of computational cardiac electrophysiology (EP) has demonstrated the ability of three-
23 dimensional (3D) cardiac computational models to perform *in-silico* EP studies. However, the
24 personalization and modeling of certain key components remain challenging, particularly in the case
25 of the infarct border zone (BZ). In this study, we used a clinical dataset from a patient with a history
26 of infarct-related VT to build an image-based 3D ventricular model aimed at computational simulation
27 of cardiac EP, including detailed *patient-specific* cardiac anatomy and infarct scar geometry. We
28 modeled the BZ in eight different ways by combining the presence or absence of electrical remodeling
29 with four different levels of image-based patchy fibrosis (0%, 10%, 20% and 30%). A 3D torso model
30 was also constructed to compute the ECG. *Patient-specific* sinus activation patterns were simulated
31 and validated against the patient's ECG. Subsequently, the pacing protocol used to induce reentrant
32 VTs in the EP laboratory was reproduced *in-silico*. The clinical VT was induced with different versions
33 of the model and from different pacing points, thus identifying the slow conducting channel responsible
34 for such VT. Finally, the real patient's ECG recorded during VT episodes was used to validate our
35 simulation results and to assess different strategies to model the BZ. Our study showed that reduced
36 conduction velocities and heterogeneity in action potential duration in the BZ are the main factors in
37 promoting reentrant activity. Either electrical remodeling or fibrosis in a degree of at least 30% in the
38 BZ were required to initiate VT. Moreover, this proof-of-concept study confirms the feasibility of
39 developing 3D computational models for cardiac EP able to reproduce cardiac activation in sinus
40 rhythm and during VT, using exclusively non-invasive clinical data.

41 1 INTRODUCTION

42 Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of both morbidity and mortality worldwide, with ischemic
43 heart disease being the most common cause among them (Abubakar et al., 2015; Nowbar et al., 2014).
44 Months or even years after suffering from a myocardial infarction (MI), when the healing process is
45 complete and the MI has reached the chronic stage (Daskalopoulos et al., 2012; van den Borne et al.,
46 2010), a significant number of patients develop potentially lethal ventricular tachycardias (VT) due to
47 the arrhythmogenic nature of remodeled tissue (de Bakker et al., 1993; Lazzara and Scherlag, 1984;
48 Nguyen et al., 2014). Infarct-related VTs are commonly associated with the so-called *slow conducting*
49 *channels* (SCC), also known as *isthmuses*, which are pathways composed of surviving myocytes across
50 the infarct scar that are responsible for the initiation and maintenance of reentrant activity, usually
51 leading to monomorphic VTs (Aliot et al., 2009; de Bakker et al., 1988). Moreover, SCC are closely
52 related to the *border zone* (BZ) (also termed *grey zone* or *peri-infarct zone*), a region constituting the
53 transition between infarct scar and healthy myocardium that comprises altered but still viable tissue
54 surrounding the dense fibrotic scar (infarct scar) resulted from the healing of MI. Several studies have
55 described the BZ as a region of slowed conduction composed of surviving but remodeled myocytes
56 with infiltration of bundles of patchy fibrosis extending from the core of compact fibrosis (infarct scar),
57 which results in a highly arrhythmogenic tissue (de Bakker et al., 1993; Nguyen et al., 2014; Rohr,
58 2012; Rutherford et al., 2012).

59 At present, cardiac delayed enhancement-MRI (DE-MRI) is commonly used to explore the infarcted
60 area pre-operatively, since it enables *in-vivo* evaluation of the tissue damaged by MI (i.e., scar and BZ)
61 due to the hyper-enhancement of the infarcted region in the images (Doltra et al., 2013; Fieno et al.,
62 2000; Kim et al., 1999a). In fact, it is currently considered as the gold-standard test for *in-vivo*
63 assessment of scar and myocardial viability after MI in clinical settings (Jamiel et al., 2017; Patel et
64 al., 2017). Cardiac DE-MRI provides a substrate characterization after MI that has shown close
65 correlation with histopathological analyzes (Amado et al., 2004; Fieno et al., 2000; Kim et al., 1999a;
66 Wagner et al., 2003), allowing to differentiate between scar and BZ. The usefulness of MRI-based
67 substrate characterization and SCCs delineation for planning and guiding ablation procedures aimed at
68 infarct-related VTs has been tested in numerous studies (Andreu et al., 2011, 2015, 2017; Ashikaga et
69 al., 2007; Fernández-Armenta et al., 2013; Perez-David et al., 2011; Soto-Iglesias et al., 2016;
70 Wijnmaalen et al., 2011; Yamashita et al., 2016).

71 Radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is a common procedure to interrupt reentrant circuits through SCC
72 responsible for VTs related to chronic MI (Baldinger et al., 2016; Berruezo et al., 2015; de Chillou et
73 al., 2002; Stevenson et al., 1993; Wilber, 2008). As part of the electrophysiological (EP) study
74 immediately prior to RFA in patients with infarct-related VT, interventional cardiologists try to induce
75 the clinical VT originally undergone by the patient by means of pacing protocols applied at selected
76 sites of myocardium. A positive induction of monomorphic VT is assumed as an evidence of the
77 presence of at least one SCC responsible for the VT (Pedersen et al., 2014; Priori et al., 2015). In such
78 a case, the SCC is ablated to block the propagation through the reentrant circuit, thus avoiding the
79 reentry and, consequently, the VT. However, these procedures are invasive, risky and very time-
80 consuming. Moreover, they show a relatively low success rate, as up to 50% of patients develop
81 recurrent VT after the RFA procedure (Baldinger et al., 2016; Gerstenfeld, 2013; Yokokawa et al.,
82 2013).

83 Electroanatomical mapping (EAM) systems (Ben-Haim et al., 1996; Gepstein et al., 1997), are
84 commonly employed in the EP laboratory to guide RFA procedures aimed at assessing both atrial
85 (Calkins et al., 2012) and ventricular arrhythmias (Aliot et al., 2009; Priori et al., 2015), due to its

86 ability to integrate spatial 3D and EP information recorded by the catheter. In the case of infarct-related
87 VTs, EAM systems are considered as a helpful tool to identify SCCs as RFA targets based on the
88 abnormal features of electrograms (EGM) in such regions (Bogun et al., 2005; Gardner et al., 1985),
89 especially when clinical VT is unmappable due to non-inducibility or hemodynamic instability (Aliot
90 et al., 2009; Marchlinski et al., 2000; Priori et al., 2015).

91

92 In contrast to EAM systems, an alternative non-invasive approach for pre-operative characterization
93 of target substrate and planning of RFA procedures is the use of 3D computational models able to
94 simulate cardiac EP accurately. Such an approach has the potential to help physicians to better
95 understand and predict the underlying mechanisms of a wide variety of cardiac disorders, as well as in
96 therapy planning and management of those diseases (Arevalo et al., 2016; Krueger et al., 2013; Lopez-
97 Perez et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2011; Trayanova et al., 2012, 2017; Trayanova and Boyle, 2013;
98 Vigmond et al., 2009). Although such *in-silico* approaches show significant potential, a number of
99 important questions related to the necessary level of detail required by the model remain unanswered.
100 In particular, the specific manner in which the microscopic structural and functional remodeling,
101 known to be present in the infarct BZ, is represented in these macroscopic clinical models, and the
102 subsequent implications of these specific choices in the initiation and the sustenance of reentrant VT
103 events, has yet to be fully investigated. Related to this, the degree of model personalization necessary
104 for accurate simulation of *patient-specific* VT episodes is also a matter of debate; for example, the
105 requirement of only personalized anatomy (from images), or whether the inclusion of functional
106 personalization (from ECG or EAM data, for instance) should also be an essential feature in model
107 construction. Full exploration of these effects is often limited by clinical data availability.

108 The main goal of this project is to develop a pipeline for performing personalized *in-silico* EP studies
109 able to aid electrophysiologists in surgical planning of RFA procedures aimed at infarct-related VTs.
110 For this purpose, we first evaluate the feasibility of building image-based 3D *patient-specific* models
111 of ventricles and torso of chronically infarcted patients, as well as the capability of such models to
112 reproduce patients' cardiac EP during VT episodes by computational simulation, including simulated
113 ECGs aiming to compare them with patients' clinical recordings. Here we present a feasibility case
114 study, building computational 3D models of ventricles and torso that are exclusively based on non-
115 invasive high-resolution clinical data. The ventricular model includes personalized and detailed 3D
116 geometry of both cardiac anatomy and the heterogeneous remodeling resulting from the MI healing
117 process (infarct scar and BZ), since both factors seem to be essential to identify SCCs as RFA targets
118 by means of *in-silico* EP studies. Additionally, as part of the EP modeling associated with our pipeline,
119 we explore the impact on VT inducibility and VT features of different modeling strategies for the BZ,
120 in which we include electrical remodeling (ER) and structural remodeling in the form of different
121 densities of image-based patchy fibrosis in order to assess the arrhythmogenic effects of those factors,
122 both separately and in combination.

123

124 2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

125 2.1 Clinical data

126 In this work, we used a set of clinical data from a 58-year-old male patient referred for a RFA procedure
127 aimed at finishing a monomorphic VT related to a large chronic MI, which extended over seven out of
128 the 17 segments of the left ventricle (LV) model of the American Heart Association (AHA).

129 Myocardial regions that appear affected in the DE-MRI were basal and medial segments of both
 130 inferoseptal and inferolateral walls and all segments of the inferior wall (basal, mid and apical), which
 131 correlates with an occlusion of the right coronary artery (Ortiz-Pérez et al., 2008). The patient suffered
 132 the acute MI 11 years before the clinical VT episode related to the MI. The clinical dataset includes:
 133 clinical high-resolution cardiac DE-MRI, whole thorax MRI, EAMs recorded via CARTO system
 134 (Biosense Webster, Inc., Diamond Bar, CA, USA) (Gepstein et al., 1997) and 12-lead ECG signals
 135 recorded during the RFA procedure both in sinus rhythm and during VT episodes induced by pacing.
 136 Importantly, all those data were not specifically generated for research purposes, but they were
 137 collected in a clinical environment as part of its daily routine.

138 Cardiac DE-MRI was acquired by a MRI scanner Magnetom Avanto 1.5T (Siemens Healthcare,
 139 Erlangen, Germany) using a phased-array body surface coil, about 15 minutes after the administration
 140 of the gadolinium-based contrast MultiHance (gadobenate dimeglumine, 529 mg/ml) (Bracco
 141 Diagnostics Inc., Monroe Township, New Jersey, USA). The acquisition was synchronized with both
 142 ECG (ECG-gated) and breathing (navigator-gated), imaging the heart at the end-diastolic phase of
 143 cardiac cycle (trigger delay = 685 ms, for a nominal R-R interval of 928 ms along the acquisition). The
 144 DE-MRI stack comprised 96 slices of 256×256 pixels encompassing the whole heart (ventricles and
 145 atria), with a pixel size of 1.4×1.4 mm and a slice thickness of 1.4 mm, thus resulting in isotropic voxel.

146 *In-vivo* EP data were recorded by CARTO 3 system using the *NaviStar ThermoCool* ablation catheter
 147 with 3.5 mm saline-irrigated tip (Abdelwahab and Sapp, 2007). A pressure sensor placed at catheter
 148 tip ensured the proper contact between the catheter and the myocardial wall. A total of 847 points were
 149 registered: 315 from LV endocardium, 78 from right ventricle (RV) endocardium and 454 from
 150 epicardium.

151 Regarding the ethical considerations, the protocol was approved by the *Ethics Committee for Clinical*
 152 *Research of the Hospital Clinic Universitari de Valencia* (Valencia, Spain), which certifies that the
 153 present study was conducted in accordance with the recommendations gathered in the Declaration of
 154 Helsinki, originally adopted by the General Assembly of the World Medical Association in 1964, and
 155 in its subsequent revisions. Furthermore, the patient, who underwent the standard clinical protocol,
 156 gave written informed consent for the use of his anonymized clinical data in this study.

157

158 **2.2 3D patient-specific ventricular model**

159 **2.2.1 Anatomical model**

160 We generated the 3D *patient-specific* bi-ventricular model by segmenting the short-axis slices from the
 161 cardiac DE-MRI using Seg3D software (Scientific Computing and Imaging Institute, University of
 162 Utah, USA) (Seg3D, 2013). We did it manually to perform a highly detailed segmentation of whole
 163 ventricles, including papillary muscles and main endocardial trabeculations (see **Figure 1** (A) and (B)).
 164 An expert radiologist in cardiac imaging checked all segmentations in order to ensure the fidelity of
 165 the 3D reconstruction of the *patient-specific* anatomy. From the segmented DE-MRI stack, we
 166 generated a surface model of ventricles that we carefully checked with Blender (Blender Foundation,
 167 Amsterdam, The Netherlands) to refine and correct defects in the mesh at the local level after applying
 168 a global smoothing. Then, using the surface model as a template, we performed a volume meshing with
 169 MeshGems-Hexa (Distene S.A.S., Bruyeres-le-Chatel, France), obtaining a hexahedra-based volume
 170 mesh comprised by 4 million nodes (vertices) and 3.71 million elements, with an average edge length
 171 of 0.4 mm.

172 To include the anisotropy of the cardiac muscle, we implemented Streeter’s rule-based method
 173 (Streeter et al., 1969) modeled by the set of equations described in (Sebastian et al., 2009), defining
 174 the helix (α_h) and transmural (α_t) angles (see **Figure 1 (D)**) for every hexahedral mesh element, based
 175 on the apex-base relative distance and transmural depth of its position within the 3D model. We first
 176 applied this method to the whole LV myocardium (including septum) and then to RV free wall. In
 177 papillary muscles and endocardial trabeculations, fibers are known to be aligned parallel to the
 178 longitudinal axis of those anatomical structures (Greenbaum et al., 1981). In order to reproduce such
 179 configuration, we performed the topological skeletonization of the volume mesh to extract the medial
 180 axes of each one of those structures, what enabled to properly assign the fiber orientation within them.
 181 Finally, we performed a Gaussian smoothing with a 3D kernel to soften abrupt transitions in fibers
 182 direction between the myocardial wall and the papillary muscles and trabeculations, as well as at the
 183 RV free wall-septum junctions.

184

185 **2.2.2 Infarct scar and border zone**

186 We generated 3D representations of the geometry of the infarct scar and BZ by segmenting the slices
 187 of the cardiac DE-MRI by means of a custom implementation of the so-called *standard deviation (SD)*
 188 *method* (Kim et al., 1999a). Briefly, we divided the segmented LV myocardium into two sub-regions
 189 (healthy and infarcted) (see **Figure 2 (A)**), based on the pixel intensity levels (i.e., grey levels). Within
 190 the infarcted region, we classified every pixel as dense fibrotic scar (intensity levels higher than
 191 mean+3×SD of healthy myocardium), BZ (levels between mean+2×SD and mean+3×SD) or healthy
 192 tissue (values under mean+2×SD) (Fieno et al., 2000; Kim et al., 1999a; Kolipaka et al., 2005; Perez-
 193 David et al., 2011; Yan, 2006). Finally, we mapped the scar and BZ into the volume mesh of the 3D
 194 ventricular model, labeling every hexahedron in the 3D model as healthy, scar or BZ depending on its
 195 position relative to the surfaces representing the infarct scar and the whole MI (see **Figure 2 (B)**).

196 In an attempt to reproduce the structural remodeling within the BZ (patchy fibrosis) based on our
 197 clinical data, we first mapped the intensity levels of the DE-MRI into the volume mesh of our 3D
 198 ventricular model (**Figure 3 (A)**). Since the DE-MRI voxels (isotropic voxels with edge length of 1.4
 199 mm) were larger than FEM mesh elements (hexahedra with average edge length of 0.4 mm), the
 200 intensity level corresponding to each DE-MRI voxel was assigned to several FEM elements that might
 201 comprise up to 64 hexahedra. We then generated different levels of fibrosis (10%, 20% and 30%)
 202 within the BZ based on that information mapped from the DE-MRI (see **Figure 3**). Among the
 203 elements of the volume mesh previously labelled as BZ, we defined as fibrotic those ones associated
 204 with the highest intensity levels, in an amount depending on the desired fibrosis level. Thus, we labelled
 205 as fibrotic a percentage of elements belonging to the BZ that matched the specified level of patchy
 206 fibrosis.

207 As shown in **Figure 3**, our approach of image-based generation of different fibrosis levels within the
 208 BZ resulted in clusters of fibrotic tissue. This method produced a distribution that may be classified as
 209 patchy fibrosis, defined as a mixture of bundles of myocardial tissue and fibrotic tissue (de Jong et al.,
 210 2011).

211

212 **2.2.3 CARTO data reannotation and integration**

213 Local activation times (LAT) annotations were automatically determined by the *Confidense* module of
 214 CARTO system. First, we discarded all points with peak-to-peak amplitude under 0.5 mV in distal

215 bipolar EGM (M1-M2), as they are considered as non-excitabile tissue corresponding to the dense
 216 fibrotic scar (Marchlinski et al., 2000; Soejima et al., 2002). For the remaining EGMs, those acquired
 217 on healthy tissue were revised by a custom code for LAT re-annotation. We chose the deflection of
 218 distal bipolar signal closest to the point of maximum negative slope in distal unipolar signal as the
 219 activation time (Paul et al., 1990; Spach et al., 1979; Stevenson and Soejima, 2005), which showed
 220 good agreement with annotations determined by the *Confidense* module in most cases. However, such
 221 criterion is not reliable for points showing noisy and fragmented signals, typically located at the BZ
 222 surrounding the infarct scar (Aliot et al., 2009). In those cases, we placed LAT annotations manually
 223 under the close supervision of a well-trained electrophysiologist, who also reviewed LAT annotations
 224 for healthy EGMs. Furthermore, we discarded those points whose LAT value showed a poor spatio-
 225 temporal coherence with their closest neighbors. After this process, only 385 out of the 847 CARTO
 226 measurement points were preserved: 84 for LV endocardium, 49 for RV endocardium and 252 for
 227 epicardium.

228 We had three surfaces generated by the CARTO system, including both acquired and interpolated data:
 229 LV endocardium, RV endocardium and epicardium (**Figure 1**. (A) Manual segmentation process of
 230 cardiac DE-MRI performed with Seg3D, displaying three slices corresponding to the standard cardiac
 231 planes: short-axis (*left*), four-chamber plane (*center*) and long-axis showing the LV (*right*). (Note that
 232 in those views the LV appears on the right side and the RV on the left). Contours highlighted in distinct
 233 colors show: LV myocardium including the septum (*red*), RV myocardium (*blue*) and papillary
 234 muscles and endocardial trabeculations of LV (*yellow*) and RV (*green*). (B) Posterior view of a coronal
 235 cross-section (four-chamber plane) of the hexahedra-based FEM volume mesh of the 3D *patient-*
 236 *specific* ventricular model. Various cardiac regions are labeled with different colors: septum (*blue*), LV
 237 free wall (*cyan*), RV free wall (*green*) and papillary muscles and main endocardial trabeculations of
 238 LV (*yellow*) and RV (*red*). (C) Transmural heterogeneity of ventricular myocardium, showing the
 239 distribution of the three different kinds of ventricular myocytes: endo-, mid- (M cells) and epicardial
 240 cells. (D) Left antero-lateral view of the 3D ventricular model displaying a representation of cardiac
 241 fibers orientation at different wall depths (endocardium, mid-myocardium and epicardium).

242

243 **Figure 2.** (A) Segmentation process from short-axis DE-MRI slices of the heterogeneous remodeling
 244 caused by MI, including infarct scar and BZ. Left panel shows the first step that involves the manual
 245 delineation of remote ROI (region-of-interest) (*green*) and infarcted ROI (*yellow*) within the LV
 246 myocardium ROI (*red*), also displaying the RV myocardium ROI (*cyan*). Right panel shows the
 247 segmentation for infarct scar (*purple*) and BZ (*yellow*) resulting from the application within the
 248 infarcted ROI of thresholds determined by SD method from the remote ROI of each slice. (B) 3D
 249 representation of the MI reconstructed from DE-MRI images, showing posterior views of the 3D
 250 surface model of ventricles (rendered with transparency) along with those hexahedral elements of
 251 volume mesh labeled as infarct scar (*red*) and BZ (*blue*).

252

253 **Figure 3.** (A) Grey intensity levels from DE-MRI mapped into the hexahedral volume mesh of the 3D
 254 ventricular model, showing a postero-basal view of the whole model (*left*) and a basal view of a cross-
 255 section in the short-axis plane (*right*). The next three panels show the 3D fibrosis distribution resulting
 256 from the introduction of several degrees of structural remodeling within the BZ: (B) 10%, (C) 20% and
 257 (D) 30% patchy fibrosis. All those panels show a posterior view of the 3D surface model of ventricles
 258 (rendered with transparency) together with those hexahedral elements labelled as BZ (*blue*) and fibrosis

259 (orange) extracted from the volume mesh of ventricular model. In each panel there is an image showing
 260 both the BZ and fibrosis (left) and another one only displaying the fibrotic elements (right).

261

262 **Figure 4 (A).** Epicardial mapping was performed by accessing pericardial space through percutaneous
 263 (non-surgical) transthoracic subxiphoid approach by means of puncture using an epidural needle
 264 (Brugada et al., 2003; Sosa and Scanavacca, 2005; Tedrow and Stevenson, 2009; Yamada, 2014),
 265 following the access procedure originally described by Sosa *et al.* (Sosa et al., 1996, 2000). We applied
 266 a rigid transformation using the ICP (iterative closest point) algorithm (Besl and McKay, 1992), to
 267 align those three CARTO surface meshes to our 3D *patient-specific* ventricular model. Then, we
 268 projected all measurement points from each CARTO mesh to the closest surface node of our ventricular
 269 model, in terms of Euclidean distance. Thus, we obtained all CARTO measurement points (those
 270 preserved after the checking process) mapped onto the external surface of our 3D bi-ventricular model
 271 (see **Figure 1.** (A) Manual segmentation process of cardiac DE-MRI performed with Seg3D,
 272 displaying three slices corresponding to the standard cardiac planes: short-axis (left), four-chamber
 273 plane (center) and long-axis showing the LV (right). (Note that in those views the LV appears on the
 274 right side and the RV on the left). Contours highlighted in distinct colors show: LV myocardium
 275 including the septum (red), RV myocardium (blue) and papillary muscles and endocardial
 276 trabeculations of LV (yellow) and RV (green). (B) Posterior view of a coronal cross-section (four-
 277 chamber plane) of the hexahedra-based FEM volume mesh of the 3D *patient-specific* ventricular
 278 model. Various cardiac regions are labeled with different colors: septum (blue), LV free wall (cyan),
 279 RV free wall (green) and papillary muscles and main endocardial trabeculations of LV (yellow) and
 280 RV (red). (C) Transmural heterogeneity of ventricular myocardium, showing the distribution of the
 281 three different kinds of ventricular myocytes: endo-, mid- (M cells) and epicardial cells. (D) Left
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 283 at different wall depths (endocardium, mid-myocardium and epicardium).

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 290 infarcted ROI of thresholds determined by SD method from the remote ROI of each slice. (B) 3D
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 299 (D) 30% patchy fibrosis. All those panels show a posterior view of the 3D surface model of ventricles
 300 (rendered with transparency) together with those hexahedral elements labelled as BZ (blue) and fibrosis

301 (*orange*) extracted from the volume mesh of ventricular model. In each panel there is an image showing
 302 both the BZ and fibrosis (*left*) and another one only displaying the fibrotic elements (*right*).

303

304 **Figure 4 (B)**). The earliest activated region was located on the septal region of the LV endocardium at
 305 mid-apical level and, the latest activated on the epicardial surface within the BZ near the scar.

306

307 **2.3 3D torso model**

308 The whole torso MRI stack was acquired in the coronal plane with a slice thickness of 10 mm. We
 309 roughly segmented the main organs (lungs, liver, heart) and structures (bones, body contour, blood
 310 pools, great vessels) using Seg3D software. The resolution of the torso MRI hampered a detailed
 311 reconstruction of some important structures, so we used the reconstructed parts of the model as
 312 landmarks to fit a detailed torso model previously developed (Ferrer et al., 2015) by means of a linear
 313 transformation. Next, we replaced the ventricles in the fitted detailed torso model by our *patient-*
 314 *specific* model and removed any intersections between our ventricular model and surrounding organs
 315 (see **Figure 5 (A)**). Finally, we used TetGen (Si and Gärtner, 2005) to mesh the torso volume with
 316 tetrahedra, which resulted in 1.26 million nodes and 7.38 million elements organs (see **Figure 5 (B)**).
 317 The average edge length was of 0.55 mm. Note that the problem of passive propagation of extracellular
 318 potentials, i.e., only diffusion without reaction component, does not require such a fine spatial
 319 resolution outside the heart domain (Prassl et al., 2009); for this reason, the mesh is highly refined only
 320 in the region of the ventricles, as shown in **Figure 5 (B)**.

321

322 **2.4 Electrophysiological modeling**

323 **2.4.1 Healthy myocardium**

324 For healthy myocardium, we used the ten Tusscher model of human ventricular action potential (AP)
 325 (ten Tusscher and Panfilov, 2006), considering the transmural heterogeneity of the ventricular
 326 myocardium (Antzelevitch et al., 1999; Drouin et al., 1995). We defined three different transmural
 327 layers for endocardial, midmyocardial (M cells) and epicardial myocytes within the volume mesh of
 328 our ventricular model, spanning 17%, 41% and 42% of ventricular wall thickness, respectively (see
 329 **Figure 1 (C)**). These values were estimated from the data reported by several experimental studies
 330 (Sicouri et al., 1994; Sicouri and Antzelevitch, 1991; Yan et al., 1998).

331 In order to establish the conductivities that will define the conduction velocities (CV), we performed a
 332 set of test simulations on a 3D slab model (20x20x6 mm) composed of regular hexahedral elements
 333 (voxels) with an edge length of 0.4 mm, matching the average length in the ventricular model. As a
 334 result, we set the conductivity values to 0.24 S/m and 0.0456 S/m for longitudinal (σ_L) and transversal
 335 (σ_T) conductivity, respectively. This resulted in a CV of 0.68 m/s along the fiber direction and of 0.26
 336 m/s in transverse direction. These values are consistent with the experimental measurements in human
 337 ventricles (Taggart et al., 2000).

338

339 2.4.2 Infarct scar and border zone

340 We considered the infarct scar as a non-excitabile tissue mainly composed of collagen, so we modeled
 341 it as an electrical insulator. To do so, we defined an internal boundary in our 3D model and imposed
 342 no-flux boundary condition at the interface between the scar and surrounding tissue, which mostly
 343 corresponded to the BZ.

344 To include the ER in the BZ, we modified the ten Tusscher model (ten Tusscher and Panfilov, 2006)
 345 by introducing reductions in the maximum conductance of certain ionic channels, as reported from
 346 several patch-clamp experiments with cells of epicardial BZs from canine hearts. According to those
 347 data, I_{Na} was reduced to 38% of its normal value (Pu and Boyden, 1997), I_{CaL} to 31% (Dun et al., 2004)
 348 and I_{Kr} and I_{Ks} to 30% and 20% (Jiang et al., 2000), respectively. At the tissue level, we reduced the
 349 conductivity parameters in the BZ to 0.05 S/m and 0.01 S/m for longitudinal (σ_L) and transversal (σ_T)
 350 conductivity, respectively. Importantly, we used the same conductivity values for the BZ for those
 351 versions of the model including fibrosis and ER and for those ones including only fibrosis in the BZ.
 352 Hence, we set reduced conductivities at tissue level for the BZ in all versions of the ventricular model
 353 regardless of whether or not it included ER at the ionic level. CVs measured on a 3D slab model using
 354 the remodeled version of ten Tusscher model were 0.17 m/s in the longitudinal direction and 0.065 m/s
 355 in the transverse directions, corresponding to a reduction of around 75% with respect to the CVs in
 356 healthy tissue. Conductivities for BZ in combination with the original ten Tusscher model yielded CVs
 357 of 0.225 m/s and 0.09 m/s for longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively, which means a
 358 reduction of around 65%.

359 For fibrosis within the BZ, we used the MacCannell model for human ventricular fibroblast
 360 (MacCannell et al., 2007). At tissue level, we considered fibrotic tissue as isotropic and set its
 361 conductivity to 0.1 S/m; a reduction of 60% with respect to the longitudinal conductivity in healthy
 362 myocardium. Fibrotic tissue behaves as a passive conductor that only enables electrotonic conduction
 363 (passive propagation), rapidly leading to blocks due to the attenuation of propagated potentials. Since
 364 the conductivity value set for fibrosis affects the coupling between myocytes and fibroblasts, it defines
 365 the magnitude of the electrotonic load exerted by the fibroblasts over the adjacent myocytes
 366 (MacCannell et al., 2007), with fibroblasts acting as electrical sinks along plateau and repolarization
 367 phases, while behaving as electrical sources during resting state (Gomez et al., 2014; Jacquemet, 2006;
 368 Mahoney et al., 2016; Miragoli et al., 2006; Rohr, 2012; Trayanova et al., 2014; Xie et al., 2009; Zeigler
 369 et al., 2016). This electrotonic interaction between myocytes and fibroblasts can cause a considerable
 370 impact on electrical conduction at tissue and organ level depending on fibroblast density, as will be
 371 observed in our simulation results.

372

373 2.4.3 Electrical modeling of the torso

374 We automatically labelled every tetrahedral element of the volume mesh as belonging to a given organ.
 375 The 3D torso model included bones, lungs, liver, whole heart (ventricles and atria) and blood pools of
 376 all cardiac chambers organs (see **Figure 5** (C)). As in (Ferrer et al., 2015), conductivity values assigned
 377 to different organs and tissues were taken from the literature (Bradley et al., 2000; Bressler and Ding,
 378 2006; Gabriel et al., 1996; Klepfer et al., 1997; MacLeod et al., 1991). We considered isotropic
 379 propagation for all organs and tissues of our 3D torso model, except for the ventricular myocardium
 380 where we preserved the anisotropy imposed by the orientation of cardiac fibers. As in (Klepfer et al.,
 381 1997), for the space not covered by any organ or anatomical structure we set a conductivity of 0.239
 382 S/m calculated as the average of the conductivities for the other tissues, including the skeletal muscle

383 that was not considered as a specific region in our torso model. Finally, to simulate ECG signals we
384 defined virtual electrodes on the surface of torso model corresponding to the precordial leads, which
385 were placed in their standard positions (see **Figure 5 (A)**).

386

387 **2.5 Computational simulations**

388 **2.5.1 Simulations at the organ level**

389 All simulations at the organ level were performed on eight different versions of our 3D *patient-specific*
390 ventricular model, generated by combining the presence or absence of ER in the BZ with four different
391 levels of image-based patchy fibrosis (0%, 10%, 20% and 30%), as detailed in **Table 1**. Thereby, we
392 could independently assess the arrhythmogenic effect of the structural remodeling (fibrosis) and ER
393 within the BZ, as well as the combination of both factors. We also performed some additional
394 simulations with the model with ER and 10% fibrosis (model #6), aiming to study the effect of
395 changing the conductivities within the BZ. We tested two new sets of values (0.12-0.03 S/m and 0.22-
396 0.0485 S/m for longitudinal-transversal conductivities), which in combination with our remodeled
397 version of the ten Tusscher model respectively resulted in CVs in the BZ reduced by 50% and 25%
398 with respect to the CVs for healthy tissue.

399 To perform the simulations at the organ level, we used the software ELVIRA (Heidenreich et al., 2010),
400 a FEM solver specifically developed for solving the anisotropic reaction-diffusion equation of the
401 monodomain model for cardiac EP (Roth, 1988). For the numerical solution of our simulations, we
402 applied the conjugate gradient method with an integration time step of 0.02 ms, using implicit
403 integration for the parabolic partial differential equation of monodomain model and explicit integration
404 with adaptive time stepping for the systems of ordinary differential equations associated with the ionic
405 models.

406

407 **2.5.1.1 Stabilization of myocyte-fibroblast coupling**

408 Adjacent myocytes and fibroblasts are known to interact by coupling and signaling between them in
409 both healthy and diseased myocardium (Kohl and Gourdie, 2014; Mahoney et al., 2016; Ongstad and
410 Kohl, 2016). Electrotonic interaction induces changes in myocytes coupled to fibroblasts, such as
411 elevation of resting potential (i.e., less negative) and APD shortening as a consequence of the effect of
412 fibroblasts as electrical sinks (MacCannell et al., 2007; Zeigler et al., 2016). Thus, we needed to
413 stabilize the myocyte-fibroblast electrotonic couplings as a first step in our simulation pipeline to let
414 those interactions reach the steady state. For all models including any fibrosis level (10%, 20% or
415 30%), first we performed a one-second simulation without any stimulus. After an initial stabilization
416 that caused a multi-foci ectopic-like activation, myocyte-fibroblast couplings remained stable in
417 absence of stimulation (see Video S1 in Supplementary Material), so the final state of those simulations
418 would later serve as a starting point for the following ones in our simulation pipeline.

419

420 **2.5.2 Simulation of the ECG**

421 To obtain ECG signals on the body surface, we used an approximation of the bidomain model
422 (Geselowitz and Miller, 1983) to compute the extracellular potentials across the torso volume. This
423 approximation, described elsewhere (Keller et al., 2010) and recently used in other works (Ferrer-

424 Albero et al., 2017; Martinez-Mateu et al., 2018), comprises several steps. First, transmembrane
 425 potentials, previously computed by simulation at the organ level using the solver ELVIRA as explained
 426 above, were interpolated from the ventricular model to the nodes of torso model corresponding to the
 427 ventricular myocardium. Then, solving the passive term (only diffusion) of the bidomain approach we
 428 obtained the extracellular potentials in the ventricles from the interpolated transmembrane voltages.
 429 Finally, applying Dirichlet boundary conditions at the ventricles-torso interface and Neumann-type
 430 conditions at the torso surface, the extracellular potentials were computed by using the FEM method
 431 to solve a Laplace equation over the volume mesh of 3D torso model. To obtain the numerical solution
 432 of the problem, we used the conjugate gradient method with the incomplete Cholesky decomposition
 433 as a preconditioner. (See Supplementary Material for more details about the method used to compute
 434 simulated ECGs).

435

436 3 RESULTS

437 3.1 3D ventricular model

438 As well as including *patient-specific* cardiac anatomy, our 3D ventricular model also integrated
 439 personalized geometry of heterogeneous remodeling caused by MI, differentiating between infarct scar
 440 and BZ that comprised 16% and 8.5% of the volume of LV myocardium, respectively. Importantly,
 441 3D reconstruction of the MI remodeling from DE-MRI revealed the presence, at the epicardial level,
 442 of an isthmus mainly composed of BZ intermingled with several thin patches of healthy tissue that was
 443 surrounded by dense scar. Both the shape and features of this structure match the definition of a SCC
 444 representing a potential substrate for reentrant VT (de Bakker et al., 1988; Fernández-Armenta et al.,
 445 2013). Moreover, as observed in **Figure 1**. (A) Manual segmentation process of cardiac DE-MRI
 446 performed with Seg3D, displaying three slices corresponding to the standard cardiac planes: short-axis
 447 (*left*), four-chamber plane (*center*) and long-axis showing the LV (*right*). (Note that in those views the
 448 LV appears on the right side and the RV on the left). Contours highlighted in distinct colors show: LV
 449 myocardium including the septum (*red*), RV myocardium (*blue*) and papillary muscles and endocardial
 450 trabeculations of LV (*yellow*) and RV (*green*). (B) Posterior view of a coronal cross-section (four-
 451 chamber plane) of the hexahedra-based FEM volume mesh of the 3D *patient-specific* ventricular
 452 model. Various cardiac regions are labeled with different colors: septum (*blue*), LV free wall (*cyan*),
 453 RV free wall (*green*) and papillary muscles and main endocardial trabeculations of LV (*yellow*) and
 454 RV (*red*). (C) Transmural heterogeneity of ventricular myocardium, showing the distribution of the
 455 three different kinds of ventricular myocytes: endo-, mid- (M cells) and epicardial cells. (D) Left
 456 antero-lateral view of the 3D ventricular model displaying a representation of cardiac fibers orientation
 457 at different wall depths (endocardium, mid-myocardium and epicardium).

458

459 **Figure 2.** (A) Segmentation process from short-axis DE-MRI slices of the heterogeneous remodeling
 460 caused by MI, including infarct scar and BZ. Left panel shows the first step that involves the manual
 461 delineation of remote ROI (region-of-interest) (*green*) and infarcted ROI (*yellow*) within the LV
 462 myocardium ROI (*red*), also displaying the RV myocardium ROI (*cyan*). Right panel shows the
 463 segmentation for infarct scar (*purple*) and BZ (*yellow*) resulting from the application within the
 464 infarcted ROI of thresholds determined by SD method from the remote ROI of each slice. (B) 3D
 465 representation of the MI reconstructed from DE-MRI images, showing posterior views of the 3D
 466 surface model of ventricles (rendered with transparency) along with those hexahedral elements of
 467 volume mesh labeled as infarct scar (*red*) and BZ (*blue*).

468

469 **Figure 3.** (A) Grey intensity levels from DE-MRI mapped into the hexahedral volume mesh of the 3D
 470 ventricular model, showing a postero-basal view of the whole model (*left*) and a basal view of a cross-
 471 section in the short-axis plane (*right*). The next three panels show the 3D fibrosis distribution resulting
 472 from the introduction of several degrees of structural remodeling within the BZ: (B) 10%, (C) 20% and
 473 (D) 30% patchy fibrosis. All those panels show a posterior view of the 3D surface model of ventricles
 474 (rendered with transparency) together with those hexahedral elements labelled as BZ (*blue*) and fibrosis
 475 (*orange*) extracted from the volume mesh of ventricular model. In each panel there is an image showing
 476 both the BZ and fibrosis (*left*) and another one only displaying the fibrotic elements (*right*).

477

478 **Figure 4** (C), integration of CARTO data onto the 3D model showed good agreement between the
 479 epicardial isthmus and a set of CARTO points labelled during the RFA procedure as candidates to be
 480 part of a SCC due to the characteristics of its bipolar EGMs (low voltage, fractionated and split signals,
 481 late and isolated potentials, etc.) (Bogun et al., 2005; de Chillou et al., 2002). The image-based *patient-*
 482 *specific* 3D model of infarcted ventricles developed in this work, as well as the 3D torso model, are
 483 both publicly available at <http://commlab.uv.es/repository/>.

484

485 3.1.1 Electrophysiological modeling of the border zone

486 ER in the BZ, represented by our modified version of ten Tusscher model, resulted in a decrease of
 487 upstroke velocity and maximum amplitude of AP mainly caused by the downregulation of I_{Na} , as well
 488 as an increase in AP duration (APD) relative to the normal values due to the reduction of repolarizing
 489 potassium currents I_{Kr} and I_{Ks} . As observed in **Figure 6**, the main effect of the applied changes is the
 490 prolongation of the APD, which affects both a single isolated cell and a cell embedded in a 3D
 491 remodeled tissue in a similar degree. Table S1 (see Supplementary Material) summarizes a quantitative
 492 analysis of the changes in several AP key biomarkers resulting from the modifications included in the
 493 ten Tusscher model for ER in the BZ, for both isolated and embedded cell.

494

495 3.2 Computational simulations

496 3.2.1 Sinus rhythm simulation

497 We reproduced the patient's ECG in sinus rhythm using computational simulation, in order to test and
 498 validate our 3D *patient-specific* model. Since we had the endocardial EAMs for both ventricles, we
 499 used that information to generate a *patient-specific* stimulation sequence aiming to reproduce the
 500 patient's sinus activation pattern accurately. We used a total of 133 manually-checked endocardial
 501 CARTO points (84 for LV and 49 for RV) mapped onto the endocardial surfaces to create that
 502 personalized sinus stimulation sequence. We used those mapped points as stimulation sites, applying
 503 a stimulus at each one of them in the time instant given by the checked LAT value associated with the
 504 corresponding endocardial CARTO point. The endocardial CARTO point with the earliest LAT was
 505 the first stimulated site (at $t = 0$ ms) and the rest of points were sequentially stimulated until reaching
 506 the latest activated point (highest LAT value) according to recorded EAMs (see Figure S1 in
 507 Supplementary Material). To perform these simulations of sinus rhythm, we took the final state of the
 508 stabilization step (myocyte-fibroblast coupling) as starting point ($t = 0$ ms). Then, we applied the

509 CARTO-derived endocardial stimulation sequence to simulate six heartbeats at a basic cycle length
 510 (BCL) of 800 ms, thus matching the patient's heart rate in sinus rhythm (75 bpm) during the RFA
 511 procedure, which was measured from the ECG recordings included in CARTO data. Note that only the
 512 sixth beat was used to simulate the ECG signals in the 3D torso model for a single heartbeat in order
 513 to compare those signals to patient's recordings.

514 The activation map corresponding to sinus rhythm simulated with model #6 (with ER and 10% fibrosis
 515 in BZ) is displayed Figure 7. As observed, most of the ventricular tissue is already activated in around
 516 140 ms. However, certain regions of the BZ show a very late activation, especially the epicardial
 517 isthmus (see Figure 7 (D)), where activation lasts up to 289 ms. Activation maps for this CARTO-
 518 derived sinus rhythm are very similar for all versions of the ventricular model. The only remarkable
 519 difference is the time that the tissue corresponding to the BZ takes to be fully activated, ranging from
 520 243 ms for model #1 (no ER and no fibrosis in BZ) to 296 ms for model #8 (with ER and 30% fibrosis
 521 in BZ). Both factors slow down the activation of the BZ, with ER causing delays longer than fibrosis.

522 Figure 8 shows APD maps for four different versions of the ventricular model, depicting the
 523 repolarization dispersion (or APD heterogeneity) generated by both the ER and the presence of fibrosis
 524 in the BZ. The inclusion of ER in the BZ creates regions with longer APDs, while the presence of 10%
 525 image-based patchy fibrosis causes the opposite effect (APD shortening) in certain regions of the BZ.
 526 Thus, the combination of both factors increases the dispersion in the repolarization pattern, which may
 527 result in a higher arrhythmogenicity. For APD maps with 20% and 30% fibrosis in BZ, see Figure S2
 528 in Supplementary Material.

529 The comparison between the real and simulated ECG (at the precordial leads) for all versions of the
 530 ventricular model including ER in the BZ is shown in **Figure 9**. The inclusion or absence of ER in BZ
 531 did not have an important impact on the simulated ECG in sinus rhythm (see Figure S3 in
 532 Supplementary Material for simulated ECGs with models without ER in BZ). Conversely, the presence
 533 of fibrosis in the BZ caused a deviation of the ST segment that matched that observed in the real ECG
 534 (see elevation in V1 and depression in V5 and V6, for instance). Furthermore, simulated QRS complex
 535 width and polarity was remarkably similar to the patient's one, with a signal correlation over 80%,
 536 except for V2 and V3 leads for which correlation was around 70%. The most important difference was
 537 the repolarization phase, since simulated ECGs showed a delayed T wave with respect to patient's one.
 538 Neither ER nor fibrosis in BZ appeared to have an important impact on repolarization, with only a
 539 slight effect on T wave magnitude depending on fibrosis level.

540

541 **3.2.2 In-silico VT induction**

542 The final goal of our simulation pipeline was to reproduce the clinical VT *in-silico* in order to study its
 543 mechanisms and to identify reentry circuits responsible for the VT as ablation targets. Among CARTO
 544 points projected onto the 3D model, we chose two locations tagged as pacing sites in the actual
 545 procedure and replicated the same programmed electrical stimulation (PES) protocol applied by the
 546 electrophysiologists in the EP laboratory. First tested pacing site (*endo#1*) was located on the LV
 547 endocardium (

548 **Figure 10**, green sphere), while the second one (*epi#1*) was on the LV posterior epicardial wall below
 549 the apical side of the MI (

550 **Figure 10**, red sphere). Aiming to explore the influence of pacing location, we included an additional
 551 point (*epi#2*) located on the LV epicardial posterior wall, over the basal side of the MI (

552 **Figure 10**, blue sphere).

553 Starting from the steady-state after the stabilization in sinus rhythm, we paced the ventricles from each
 554 pacing site (one at a time) with a train of six stimuli delivered with a BCL of 600 ms (S1 phase),
 555 followed by a single stimulus (S2 phase) coupled at 400 ms after the last S1. If it failed to induce VT,
 556 we reduced the S2 coupling interval (CI) in steps of 10 ms until reaching positive VT induction or
 557 propagation block at pacing site. In the latter case, when VT was non-inducible by a single S2 stimulus,
 558 we repeated the PES protocol adding another premature stimulus (S3 phase) after the S2 phase, with
 559 both S2 and S3 stimuli coupled at the same CI. We followed that protocol for the eight model versions
 560 (**¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**) and the three pacing sites (

561 **Figure 10**). **Table 1** summarizes the results of all those *in-silico* tests of VT inducibility. Focusing on
 562 VT simulations at the organ level, such results show that our pipeline was able to replicate the outcomes
 563 of the VT inducibility tests performed in the EP laboratory. We achieved positive VT induction with
 564 several versions of the ventricular model from the two pacing sites (*endo#1* and *epi#1*) that succeeded
 565 in the real EP study. On the contrary, pacing site *epi#2* (not tested in the clinic) could not trigger VT
 566 on any model version.

567 Regardless the pacing site, all induced VTs showed a common mechanism characterized by a
 568 unidirectional block at the lower side (the most apical end) of the epicardial SCC previously described,
 569 consequently leading to reentry through its upper side (the most basal end). **Figure 11** (A-E) displays
 570 potential maps at different times, showing the propagation patterns generated by the S2 stimulus that
 571 gives rise to the unidirectional block and, subsequently, to the onset of the VT due to reentry. Such
 572 epicardial SCC enabled the perpetuation of the reentrant activity, showing a clockwise macroreentrant
 573 propagation pattern with the wavefront entering the SCC through its upper end and leaving it through
 574 the lower one (see **Figure 11** (F)), what triggered a self-sustained monomorphic VT with a BCL of
 575 526 ms (114 bpm) on model #6 (see Video S2 in Supplementary Material).

576 In our model, the presence of ER in the BZ was necessary in three out of four configurations allowing
 577 positive VT induction (models #5-7). The only configuration providing positive VT induction without
 578 ER (model #4) required the highest fibrosis level (30%) in the BZ among tested ones, together with a
 579 CI for S2-S3 phases significantly shorter than that of cases including ER in BZ (see **Table 1**).
 580 Concerning pacing site *epi#2* that we added to those tested in the real EP study, the VT test was
 581 negative in all model versions, since the applied PES protocol never managed to induce unidirectional
 582 block at either of the ends of the epicardial SCC (see Video S3 in Supplementary Material). Model #8
 583 was a special case, as it is the only configuration that always led to bidirectional block at the lower end
 584 of the epicardial SCC regardless both the pacing site and the CI for S2-S3 phases, blocking the
 585 propagation even in the S1 phase (see Video S4 in Supplementary Material).

586 **Figure 12** shows APD maps for three different versions of the ventricular model, exhibiting
 587 considerable repolarization dispersion caused by either ER or fibrosis in the BZ, as already observed
 588 in sinus activation (see Figure 8 and Figure S2). Those maps, resulting from the propagation of the
 589 last stimulus of S1 phase, differ significantly between them, although sharing a common feature. All
 590 of them present regions of longer APDs (compared to the rest of BZ tissue) at both ends of the
 591 epicardial SCC that supports the reentrant activity. This effect seems more marked at the lower side of
 592 the SCC, where the unidirectional block that triggers the reentry occurs, especially in those models

593 including ER in the BZ (**Figure 12** (B and C)). It is probably caused by a deeper impact of source-sink
 594 mismatches because of the narrower funnel shape of the lower end of the SCC compared to the upper
 595 one.

596 Following the premise of only including non-invasive clinical data in our pipeline, we obtained the
 597 simulated ECGs for all successful VT induction using the torso model in order to assess the matching
 598 between the *in-silico* induced and the clinical VT by comparing both ECGs. The frequency of reentry
 599 around the scar was faster in the patient (BCL=340 ms, 175 bpm) than in the simulations (BCL=506-
 600 526 ms, 114-118 bpm) (see **Table 1**), probably due to differences in CVs mainly in the BZ including
 601 the SCC. It is noteworthy that CVs, as well as APDs, were not personalized but based on population
 602 data. Aiming to compare the morphology of precordial leads, we removed the frequency variability by
 603 resampling a simulated ECG and overlapped it to the patient's ECG. **Figure 13** shows such
 604 comparison, where it is clearly appreciated that both morphologies present a high degree of correlation,
 605 with the simulated ECG following every signal deflection in the real signals in all precordial leads.
 606 Only lead V2 showed an enlarged amplitude in the simulated case in one of the sections of the signal.
 607 Hence, as in the case of sinus activation, V2 shows the most considerable differences with respect to
 608 the patient's ECG, along with V3 to a lesser extent. All configurations that managed to induce VT
 609 showed the same reentrant pattern depicted in **Figure 11** (F), therefore resulting in highly similar
 610 ECGs, just revealing subtle differences in VT frequency, as observed in **Figure 13** and detailed in
 611 **Table 1**.

612 After analyzing our simulation results, given the significant difference in frequency between clinical
 613 and simulated VT (175 vs 115 bpm), we chose model #6 and pacing site *epi#1* to perform some
 614 additional tests aiming to study the influence of different CVs in the BZ on VT features and its related
 615 mechanisms. With CVs reduced by 25% with respect to healthy tissue, the result for VT induction was
 616 negative, since unidirectional block never happened (see Video S5 in Supplementary Material),
 617 reaching propagation fail at pacing site at CI of 290 ms. In contrast, the test with CVs reduced by 50%
 618 resulted in a positive VT induction, triggered again by unidirectional block at the lower side of the
 619 epicardial SCC, due to S2-S3 stimuli with 320 ms for CI. Such interval is notably shorter than the
 620 successful CI in the case of CVs reduced in 75% (see **Table 1**), in which VT furthermore resulted from
 621 a single S2 stimulus. Regarding the simulated ECG, the morphology of the monomorphic VT did not
 622 exhibit significant variations. However, the acceleration of the reentrant activity due to increased CVs
 623 in the BZ led to a considerably shorter BCL (425 ms, 141 bpm) (see **Figure 13**), closer to that of the
 624 clinical VT but still a 20% slower (175 vs 141 bpm).

625

626 4 DISCUSSION

627 4.1 3D modeling

628 In this study, we have built a detailed image-based 3D cardiac model that faithfully reproduces the
 629 *patient-specific* anatomy and function of the ventricles of a given subject (see **Figure 1**) from non-
 630 invasive clinical data, reaching a high level of anatomical detail. In contrast, fiber orientation and
 631 transmural EP heterogeneity were included based on population data. Unlike ours, most previous 3D
 632 ventricular models ignore papillary muscles and endocardial trabeculations, especially those based on
 633 *in-vivo* clinical images. Subtlety and high inter-subject variability of endocardial structures add
 634 difficulty to the already challenging task of segmenting *in-vivo* cardiac datasets. In our particular case,

635 since the reentrant circuit is entirely confined at the epicardial level, neither papillary muscles nor
 636 trabeculations appear to have any impact on VT mechanisms. However, significant influence of some
 637 endocardial structures (e.g., moderator band in RV) on activation patterns has been observed both
 638 experimentally (Durrer et al., 1970) and by computational simulation (Bishop et al., 2010), as well as
 639 their potential role in the VT features (Bogun et al., 2008; Kim et al., 1999b; Walton et al., 2018).
 640 Further investigations with large cohorts of patients are required to assess the convenience of
 641 systematically including endocardial details in *patient-specific* models devoted to infarct-related VT
 642 simulations.

643 An essential element of our model was the anatomical and functional modeling of the infarcted region.
 644 We based our *patient-specific* anatomical MI model on cardiac DE-MRI (see **Figure 2**), which is the
 645 current gold-standard technique for *in-vivo* assessment of myocardial ischemic injury in clinical
 646 environments (Jamiel et al., 2017; Patel et al., 2017). Moreover, DE-MRI is a routine imaging
 647 technique recommended for infarcted patients referred for RFA procedures (Pedersen et al., 2014;
 648 Priori et al., 2015), so it satisfies our requisite of exclusively using non-invasive clinical data. DE-MRI
 649 enables the segmentation of the MI differentiating between infarct scar and BZ, that is crucial in order
 650 to study infarct-related VT mechanisms by computational simulation (Ringenberg et al., 2014; Ukwatta
 651 et al., 2016). Nonetheless, the proper definition of both types of tissue from *in-vivo* clinical DE-MRI
 652 images remains controversial (especially for the BZ), something that has given rise to a great variety
 653 of methods for this problem (Karim et al., 2016).

654

655 4.2 Electrophysiological modeling

656 Although it is not a completely acellular tissue (Rog-Zielinska et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2002), the infarct
 657 scar is mainly composed of extracellular matrix (collagen) (Cleutjens et al., 1999; Daskalopoulos et
 658 al., 2012; van den Borne et al., 2010). However, there is no representation for the extracellular space
 659 in the monodomain model. In such a case, a passive model (cellular level) combined with a low
 660 conductivity (tissue level) could be used to account for a slight electrotonic load caused by the scar
 661 (Deng et al., 2015; Ringenberg et al., 2014). We performed some initial tests assigning the MacCannell
 662 model to the scar region, as done in (McDowell et al., 2011). When we computed the ECG, the signals
 663 showed considerable distortion caused by strong gradients resulting from the presence of such a large
 664 region (the scar occupies the 16% of LV in our model) that practically remained at resting potential
 665 across the simulations. This unwanted “side effect” would be critical for this work, since simulating
 666 the ECG properly is a key goal in order to compare our results to a real patient’s recordings. Hence,
 667 we decided to disregard the potential electrotonic effect of the scar and modeled it as an electrical
 668 insulator by imposing no-flux boundary condition, as done in many other studies (Arevalo et al., 2013,
 669 2016; Ashikaga et al., 2013; Rantner et al., 2012; Relan et al., 2011).

670 A few simulation studies focused on infarct-related VTs have also included fibrosis within the BZ.
 671 Some authors have randomly included fibrosis, either diffuse fibrosis modeled as an electrically passive
 672 tissue in a 3D model of rabbit ventricles (McDowell et al., 2011) or as micro-regions (patches) of non-
 673 conducting scarred tissue in a 3D canine model (Arevalo et al., 2013). Similarly, a very recent work
 674 included randomly generated patterns of non-conducting fibrotic tissue within the BZ in a model of
 675 infarcted rabbit ventricles (Campos et al., 2018). Another study faithfully reproduced fibrosis
 676 distribution in the BZ by means of highly detailed 3D models of wedge samples resulting from the
 677 reconstruction of high-resolution histological sections of infarcted rat hearts, considering it as non-
 678 conducting dense fibrotic tissue (Rutherford et al., 2012).

679 The gadolinium-based contrast agent used in DE-MRI is not specific for fibrosis, so the hyper-
680 enhancement is assumed to be caused by its distribution through the extracellular space (Mewton et
681 al., 2011; Moon et al., 2004), which is expanded in fibrotic regions resulting from the healing of MI
682 (Daskalopoulos et al., 2012; Hein and Schaper, 2001; Seidel et al., 2016). Experimental observations
683 based on histological sections have witnessed the presence of fibrosis infiltrated within the BZ (de
684 Bakker et al., 1988; Rutherford et al., 2012; Smith et al., 1991; Tschabrunn et al., 2016), mainly
685 showing the appearance of patchy/interstitial fibrosis. Importantly, this is considered the most
686 arrhythmogenic kind of structural remodeling. Patchy fibrosis increases the susceptibility to
687 unidirectional blocks due to source-sink mismatches and slows down conduction because of
688 propagation delays caused by the tortuous pathways that the wavefront has to take, also leading to
689 EGM fragmentation due to impaired activation (de Bakker et al., 2005; de Jong et al., 2011; Dhanjal
690 et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2014). According to histological observations, it is widely assumed that
691 voxels showing intermediate intensity levels in DE-MRI images, usually classified as BZ, correspond
692 to a mixture of myocytes and fibrotic tissue (Hsu et al., 2006; Schuleri et al., 2009; Varga-Szemes et
693 al., 2016). Consequently, we assumed that voxels in the BZ showing the highest intensity levels in the
694 images probably correspond to pieces of myocardium having a high percentage of fibrotic tissue. Here,
695 the intensity level of each DE-MRI voxel was mapped into a cluster of hexahedral elements in the
696 volume mesh of ventricular model. This, along with the fact that the brightest voxels in the BZ are
697 usually surrounded by others with similar intensities, makes our image-based method to generate
698 patches within the BZ (see **Figure 3**), resulting in a pattern of patchy fibrosis similar to that observed
699 in histological examinations (Rutherford et al., 2012; Schuleri et al., 2009). Finally, we defined image-
700 based fibrosis up to 30% of the BZ (represented by the MacCannell model), since larger levels
701 generated fibrotic barriers completely blocking the electrical propagation inside the epicardial SCC
702 responsible for the VT, as for instance in the case of model #8 described above. A recent study used a
703 similar approach to include realistic fibrosis patterns based on DE-MRI images, although in that case
704 the aim was to assess the influence of several strategies of fibrosis modeling on atrial fibrillation
705 dynamics using a 3D model of human left atrium (Roney et al., 2016).

706 Regarding myocyte-fibroblast coupling, there is experimental evidence of the existence of this kind of
707 heterocellular coupling via gap junctions in the remodeled myocardium resulting from MI (Camelliti
708 et al., 2004; Mahoney et al., 2016; Schwab et al., 2013), as well as by tunneling nanotubes (Quinn et
709 al., 2016). However, there is a lack of experimental studies focused on the characterization of myocyte-
710 fibroblast coupling in the BZ of chronic MIs in terms of density and distribution of functional gap
711 junctions connecting both types of cells (Ongstad and Kohl, 2016). Hence, magnitude and anisotropy
712 of the electrotonic load caused by myocyte-fibroblast coupling in the BZ remain undetermined. Finally,
713 we decided to consider this influence by means of a fibroblast model (MacCannell et al., 2007) and a
714 conductivity value set for fibrotic tissue that mainly affects the myocyte-fibroblast coupling within the
715 BZ by modulating the electrotonic interaction between both cell types.

716 Besides fibrosis, we also considered the ER in the viable but altered myocardium corresponding to the
717 BZ that surrounds the infarct scar. However, it must be noted that all changes affecting ionic channels
718 considered for the BZ are based on experiments with cells harvested from epicardial BZ of canine
719 hearts (Dun et al., 2004; Jiang et al., 2000; Pu and Boyden, 1997). As recently discussed elsewhere
720 (Connolly and Bishop, 2016), it is unclear to what extent such data are representative of the ER in BZ
721 of human hearts. The presence of epicardial collateral circulation in canine hearts, not present in
722 humans, is known to influence the formation of the epicardial BZ in dogs (Schaper et al., 1988; Ursell
723 et al., 1985), which could give rise to functional differences with respect to the surviving myocytes in
724 human BZ. On the other hand, all of those experimental studies (Dun et al., 2004; Jiang et al., 2000;
725 Pu and Boyden, 1997) were performed a few days after the coronary occlusion, still in the healing

726 phase of the MI rather than in its chronic stage (see (Mendonca Costa et al., 2018) for a recent review).
 727 Nevertheless, these data have been widely used in previous studies (Arevalo et al., 2013; Ashikaga et
 728 al., 2013; Deng et al., 2015; Hill et al., 2016; McDowell et al., 2011; Rantner et al., 2012; Ringenberg
 729 et al., 2014) due to the lack of experimental data for ER in the BZ of chronically infarcted human
 730 hearts.

731 Our simulation results showed that VT inducibility was strongly related to slow conduction and APD
 732 heterogeneity in the BZ (including the SCC). Slow conduction in BZ is widely considered as a key
 733 factor in promoting reentry through SCC crossing the infarct scar, as it allows the working myocardium
 734 at the other side to recover its excitability before the arrival of the wavefront coming from the channel
 735 (de Bakker et al., 1993; Lazzara and Scherlag, 1984; Nguyen et al., 2014). However, the underlying
 736 mechanisms of this reduction in CVs still remain unclear, leading to a lack of consensus on the proper
 737 way to model it computationally. Some authors have reduced drastically only the transversal CV (Deng
 738 et al., 2015; McDowell et al., 2011). This approach could represent the severe reduction measured in
 739 gap junctional conductance in canine BZs only in the transverse direction (Yao et al., 2003) and/or the
 740 loss of side-to-side coupling between adjacent layers of myocytes due to the isolating effect of
 741 infiltrated fibrotic tissue (Spach and Boineau, 1997). Rutherford *et al.* managed to induce reentry in
 742 wedge models of infarcted myocardium due to the propagation delays exclusively caused by dense
 743 fibrosis (collagen) infiltrated within the BZ (Rutherford et al., 2012). Downregulation and lateralization
 744 of connexin 43 (i.e., gap junctions) have been also reported in the BZ (Severs et al., 2008; Smith et al.,
 745 1991). Downregulation of connexin 43 could result in an isotropic reduction of CV and its lateralization
 746 would exacerbate this effect in the longitudinal direction while keeping or even increasing transversal
 747 CV. Nonetheless, part of lateralized gap junctions of remodeled cardiomyocytes in the BZ are thought
 748 to be non-functional (Matsushita et al., 1999). Regarding tissue architecture, both DTI (diffusion tensor
 749 imaging) (Winklhofer et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2006) and histological preparations (Rutherford et al.,
 750 2012; Tschabrunn et al., 2016) have revealed fiber disarray within the BZ that consequently involves
 751 alterations in tissue anisotropy. Conversely, a recent study based on very high-resolution DTI observed
 752 good preservation of normal fiber orientation patterns in chronically infarcted regions of porcine and
 753 human hearts (Pashakhanloo et al., 2017). In conclusion, the slowed conduction in the BZ seems to
 754 derive from a complex combination of structural, electrical and gap junction remodeling that is not
 755 well understood yet (de Bakker, 2017). In our case, aiming to reproduce macroscopically the global
 756 effect of all those combined factors affecting the propagation and promoting the reentrant activity, and
 757 in addition to the image-based patchy fibrosis, we imposed an isotropic reduction of CVs in the BZ as
 758 recently done by others (Hill et al., 2016; Ringenberg et al., 2014), testing reductions of 75%, 50% and
 759 25% for both longitudinal and transversal CVs with respect to the healthy myocardium.

760

761 4.3 Sinus rhythm simulation

762 Regarding the personalization of cardiac activation, other authors have exploited EAMs to personalize
 763 electrical propagation in simplified models by adapting the so-called apparent conductivities (Chen et
 764 al., 2016; Chinchapatnam et al., 2008; Relan et al., 2011). Since we excluded invasively recorded data
 765 from our pipeline, we just benefited from CARTO data to validate the full 3D model (ventricles-torso
 766 set) in sinus rhythm by means of the simulated ECG resulting from the activation pattern provided by
 767 endocardial EAMs. The main limitations of EAMs are the lack of accurate automatic tools to fit the
 768 data to a 3D model and to annotate LATs, especially in regions showing pathological EGMs due to the
 769 presence of fibrosis and scarred tissue. The myocardium affected by the MI (scar and BZ) is the most
 770 thoroughly mapped region aiming to find SCCs across the scar as potential substrates for reentry

771 (Baldinger et al., 2016; Pokorney et al., 2016; Soejima et al., 2002). However, in that region most of
 772 EGMs show low amplitude and/or very fragmented signals (Aliot et al., 2009; Bogun et al., 2005;
 773 Gardner et al., 1985). That is why we had to exclude such a large amount of CARTO points: 462 points
 774 removed out of 847 included in the original CARTO data. In this regard, new multi-array catheters,
 775 such as *PentaRay* for CARTO system (Biosense Webster, Inc., Diamond Bar, CA, USA) or *IntellaMap*
 776 *Orion* for Rhythmia system (Boston Scientific, Marlborough, MA, USA) (Mantziari et al., 2015), are
 777 currently helping to acquire less noisy and much denser maps. Despite current limitations, including
 778 the uncertainty in LAT annotations, our whole-body level approach allowed obtaining ECGs in sinus
 779 rhythm where precordial leads showed a good signal correlation with real ECGs (between 80% and
 780 96% for V1, V4, V5 and V6), as well as a similar R-wave progression (see **Figure 9**; **Error! No se**
 781 **encuentra el origen de la referencia.**). This, along with the good agreement in QRS complex duration,
 782 indicates that chosen values for CVs in healthy myocardium and for conductivities of organs and
 783 structures in torso model are within a proper range. Moreover, the coincidence in T wave polarity
 784 between real and simulated ECGs (except for V1) suggests an appropriate definition of transmural
 785 layers, since transmural heterogeneity is known to have a great influence on the repolarization phase
 786 in organ-level simulations (Okada et al., 2011; Perotti et al., 2015). As observed in **Figure 9**, simulated
 787 signals for V2 and V3 are the leads that show most notable differences compared to real ECG, not only
 788 in the repolarization phase but also in QRS complex, as real ECG shows a prominent negative S wave
 789 that simulations could not properly reproduce. This might be partially caused by the fact that in the EP
 790 laboratory a pad for defibrillation shocks is usually fixed on the left side of patient's chest, forcing the
 791 relocation of V2 and (sometimes) V3 electrodes away from their standard positions. Hence, since we
 792 placed the virtual electrodes for simulated ECG on the standard position of precordial leads (see **Figure**
 793 **5**), this is likely to be an important error source specifically affecting V2 and V3. Moreover, considering
 794 that V2 and V3 were also the most different signals obtained from simulated VTs compared to the real
 795 ECG (see **Figure 13**), it seems highly probable that V2 and V3 electrodes were not placed in its
 796 standard positions in the EP laboratory. In conclusion, we consider this reproduction of the patient's
 797 ECG for sinus activation is an important step for the validation of our pipeline, even though it is usually
 798 omitted in other studies that also aim for planning of RFA interventions.

799

800 4.4 *In-silico* VT induction

801 The results of our simulation pipeline for *in-silico* tests of VT inducibility suggest that, in the presence
 802 of a SCC with slowed conduction, a key factor to cause a unidirectional block able to trigger a reentrant
 803 VT is the repolarization dispersion due to APD heterogeneity, as observed in **Figure 12**. In models #5-
 804 7 such APD heterogeneity (see **Figure 12** (B, C)) comes from the increased APD associated with the
 805 ER in the BZ (see **Figure 6**), even causing permanent blocks when combined with high fibrosis levels
 806 (model #8). Nevertheless, in model #4, the APD heterogeneity responsible for the unidirectional block
 807 is exclusively caused by the presence of patchy fibrosis within the BZ, which by contrast gives rise to
 808 patches of tissue with decreased APD because of myocyte-fibroblast interactions (**Figure 12** (A)). This
 809 explains the need of a shorter CI to induce VT in model #4 compared to those versions including ER
 810 in the BZ (see **Table 1**). On the other hand, the complete failure of pacing site *epi#2*, along with the
 811 fact that models #4 and #5 allowed positive VT induction from *epi#1* but not from *endo#1*, gives
 812 evidence of the important influence of the location of pacing sites on the result of VT inducibility tests
 813 and even on the morphology of induced VTs. If PES protocol delivered from *epi#2* had been able to
 814 cause a unidirectional block at the upper end of the epicardial SCC, for instance, the morphology of
 815 the resulting monomorphic VT would have been different. In such a case, macroreentry would show a
 816 counterclockwise propagation pattern that, consequently, would alter the morphology of the ECG

817 during the VT episode. Nonetheless, not only the location of pacing sites but also the geometry of the
818 SCC seems to have an essential role in VT mechanisms, what might be the reason for which in our
819 model propagation blocks occur at the lower side of the SCC but never at the upper one. In our case,
820 the lower end of the SCC is narrower than the upper (see **Figure 11**), which makes it more prone to
821 functional propagation blocks due to source-sink mismatches caused by abrupt changes in the geometry
822 of excitable tissue (Ciaccio et al., 2018; Connolly et al., 2015). With respect to the tests performed with
823 different conductivities, simulation results confirm the great impact of CVs in the BZ both on the
824 initiation mechanisms and on the frequency of infarct-related reentrant VTs.

825 Therefore, according to our simulation results, derived from a unique MI geometry, the most influential
826 factors in promoting reentrant infarct-related VTs are the reduction of CVs and APD heterogeneity
827 (repolarization dispersion) in the BZ, either caused by ER (model #5) or by the presence of fibrosis
828 (model #4), as well as by the combination of both kinds of remodeling (structural and ER) (models #6-
829 7). However, our results suggest that arrhythmogenicity is more strongly correlated with ER than with
830 fibrosis in the BZ. Only in one case (model #4 paced from point *epi#1*) we managed to induce VT in
831 the absence of ER, requiring a high fibrosis level (30%) to create an APD heterogeneity enough to
832 promote a unidirectional propagation block (**Figure 12 (A)**), in combination with a shorter CI for
833 premature stimulus. This is in agreement with that observed in (Arevalo et al., 2013) and recently
834 discussed in (Trayanova et al., 2017), whose authors concluded that the presence of fibrosis in the BZ
835 is not a necessary element in order to predict reentrant circuits by means of cardiac computational
836 models, as long as ER in BZ is considered. Focusing on model versions including ER (models #5-8),
837 moderate levels of patchy fibrosis in the BZ are thought to facilitate the initiation of VTs, as in the case
838 of models #6 (10%) and #7 (20%) paced from point *endo#1*. However, elevated levels appear to prevent
839 from VT mechanisms, as observed in model #8 (30%), where the formation of a permanent
840 bidirectional block avoids the self-sustained reentry and, consequently, the VT. This matches the
841 conclusions reached in (McDowell et al., 2011), where the authors observed an increased risk of
842 infarct-related VTs for intermediate levels of diffuse fibrosis randomly distributed within the BZ, as
843 well as a protective role against VT derived from higher levels. Hence, our approach of image-based
844 patchy fibrosis seems to have a similar impact on infarct-related VT mechanisms.

845 Although the morphology of the signals of simulated ECG is highly similar to that of clinical VT (only
846 V2 and V3 show notable differences, probably due to inaccurate electrode location) (see **Figure 13**),
847 the BCL of *in-silico* induced reentry is larger than the patient's one, thus resulting in a slower VT. We
848 think it is due to differences in CVs in the BZ and, consequently, in the epicardial SCC supporting the
849 reentry, where the model is likely to conduct slower than the real case. When we increased CVs in the
850 BZ up to 75% with respect to healthy tissue (i.e., a reduction of 25%), we could not induce VT because
851 premature stimuli (S2-S3) stopped propagating at a CI too short to produce the functional block at the
852 SCC entrance. The faster the propagation, the shorter the CI needed to generate a wavefront able to
853 reach the SCC entrance within the time window in which its tissue is vulnerable to functional blocks.
854 On the other hand, in the simulated ECGs in sinus rhythm we observed a delayed repolarization with
855 respect to the patient's ECG (**Figure 9**), something that suggests that APDs in our model are larger
856 than the patient's ones. We did not include the personalization of any parameter relative to cardiac EP
857 in the design of our pipeline. However, we hypothesize that the choice of an ionic model with a basal
858 APD shorter than ten Tusscher's one probably might allow inducing a reentry with a shorter CI for
859 premature stimuli in spite of relatively high CVs in the BZ, triggering a reentry with a shorter BCL
860 and, thus, a faster VT. Hence, we believe that including in our pipeline a coarse personalization of the
861 APD based on the features of patient's ECG in sinus rhythm, as well as for CVs in healthy myocardium,
862 could improve the performance of our approach. Although there are a few precedents in this regard

863 (Chen et al., 2016; Gillette et al., 2018; Relan et al., 2011), further studies should be conducted in order
864 to test such hypothesis.

865 As in this work, the ability to reproduce infarct-related VTs by means of image-based human cardiac
866 computational models has been demonstrated in a number of previous studies (Arevalo et al., 2016;
867 Ashikaga et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2016; Deng et al., 2016; Prakosa et al., 2018; Relan et al., 2011;
868 Ringenberg et al., 2014). Concerning the global performance of our particular approach, we have been
869 able to reproduce patient's ECG both in sinus rhythm and in clinical VT with good fidelity, considering
870 that cardiac EP and myocardial architecture were not personalized. When PES protocols produce
871 positive VT induction in the EP laboratory, electrophysiologists usually compare the resulting ECG to
872 that registered during clinical VT episodes as a method to discern whether both VTs match or not, what
873 helps in the process of choosing optimal ablation targets. Therefore, our pipeline completely based on
874 non-invasive clinical data has the potential to replicate such process *in-silico*, such that it might become
875 a helpful tool in therapy planning prior to RFA procedures aimed at finishing infarct-related VTs.

876

877 **4.5 Limitations**

878 The major limitation of our work derives from the fact that it relies on only one case. Thus, this work
879 must be considered as a proof-of-concept study that shows promising, yet preliminary results. Hence,
880 further studies including a larger number of patients should be conducted in order to improve and
881 validate our pipeline, as well as to strengthen our conclusions.

882 Some features of the 3D ventricular model were not personalized. Myocardial architecture, for
883 instance, was generated by means of a rule-based approach based on population data. The only
884 alternative is the use of DTI (Holmes et al., 2000; Hsu et al., 1998; Scollan et al., 1998), although *in-*
885 *vivo* cardiac DTI remains highly challenging because of the artifacts caused by cardiac motion.
886 However, some studies have compared simulation results performed on 3D ventricular models using
887 rule-based methods and *ex-vivo* DTI (Bayer et al., 2012; Bishop et al., 2009), finding only minor
888 differences in electrical patterns at global level, what confirms the validity and robustness of rule-based
889 approaches for simulations of cardiac EP.

890 Currently, the electrical propagation through ventricular myocardium is known to be characterized by
891 three distinct conductivities in longitudinal, transverse (within myocardial sheets) and normal (along
892 transmural direction) axes (Caldwell et al., 2009; Hooks, 2007). Recent computational studies have
893 shown the impact on propagation patterns that might result from considering such full electrical
894 anisotropy, both in simulations at organ level in healthy ventricles (Johnston et al., 2016) and in
895 simplified models of cardiac tissue under diseased conditions (Johnston et al., 2018). Instead, we
896 considered a unique conductivity for all directions perpendicular to myocyte longitudinal axis, as it has
897 been commonly assumed in most of the 3D computational studies of cardiac EP so far. Hence, the
898 incorporation of full anisotropy to the cardiac EP modeling of our pipeline might be one of the future
899 improvements, as well as the study of its influence on infarct-related VT inducibility.

900 We did not incorporate the cardiac conduction system in our ventricular model, although it was not
901 expected to have a significant impact on the infarct-related VT mechanisms that we aimed to study in
902 this work. Considering the longer APD of Purkinje cells and the delay at the Purkinje-myocardial
903 junctions, the kind of VTs simulated in this study could not have been mediated by the Purkinje system.
904 In any case, currently there is no *in-vivo* imaging modality capable of providing information about the
905 *patient-specific* geometry of Purkinje network. There are a few recent studies proposing approaches to

906 infer models of conduction system from endocardial EAMs (Barber et al., 2017; Palamara et al., 2015;
907 Vergara et al., 2014), yet it would break our requisite of only using non-invasive clinical data collected
908 prior to the RFA procedure. Then, the only alternative would be to include a synthetic Purkinje model.
909 Nevertheless, in such a case it would be impossible to assess to what extent the impact on simulation
910 results of that artificial Purkinje network (if any) would be faithfully replicating the influence of the
911 patient's conduction system in such scenario.

912 The poor quality of the anatomical whole-torso MRI hampered the construction of a *patient-specific*
913 torso model, forcing us to reuse and adapt an existing one. However, given the results yielded for
914 simulated ECGs, it does not appear to have been an important drawback, at least in this particular case.

915

916 5 CONCLUSIONS

917 Our 3D *patient-specific* model of the ventricles exclusively built from clinical data, in spite of avoiding
918 the personalization of cardiac EP (based on population data), was able to reproduce the morphology of
919 the clinical monomorphic VT suffered by the patient in the simulated ECGs. Furthermore, this allowed
920 identification within the 3D model of the SCC responsible for the reentrant activity, matching the
921 ablation target chosen by the experts in the RFA procedure that successfully eliminated VT inducibility
922 in the patient. Hence, we have given a proof of the feasibility of developing 3D *patient-specific*
923 computational models from clinical data aimed at simulation of the cardiac EP, with the potential to
924 become a powerful tool for surgical planning. This approach could help to improve the currently low
925 success rate of RFA procedures as well as to shorten surgery duration and, consequently, decrease the
926 risk to the patient. It must be highlighted the great importance of the personalization of both cardiac
927 anatomy and MI geometry from *in-vivo* high-resolution images to accurately locate reentry pathways
928 as ablation targets by *in-silico* EP studies.

929 From the functional perspective, the computational modeling of the BZ remains a complex task due to
930 the lack of experimental data from human hearts. In our study, the determinant aspects were the
931 reduction of CVs and APD heterogeneity, which could be caused by ER in the BZ, a large amount of
932 patchy fibrosis (30%) or a combination of both factors. The most arrhythmogenic versions of our
933 ventricular model were those that combined the ER with intermediate fibrosis levels (10% and 20%)
934 in the BZ. Such configurations generate an important repolarization dispersion (APD heterogeneity)
935 around the infarct scar, especially in the vicinity of both terminal ends of the epicardial SCC, making
936 the model more prone to the onset of reentrant activity due to functional unidirectional blocks in the
937 channel.

938 Several challenging issues are still hampering the introduction of cardiac computational models as a
939 common tool in clinical environments, such as the automatic and accurate reconstruction of *patient-*
940 *specific* anatomy and infarct geometry from *in-vivo* images, especially from MRI modalities. Another
941 important drawback is the current high cost of 3D computational simulations of cardiac EP at organ
942 and body levels, whose computational burden demands the use of high-performance computational
943 resources and long computing times.

944 **6 Author contributions**

945 ALP, RS, MI and JMF jointly conceived this work and assessed the results. ALP built the 3D models
946 and performed the computational simulations for this work, all of this with the priceless help and close
947 supervision from RS and JMF. ALP and RS wrote the manuscript. MI and RR collected and provided
948 clinical data used in this work and gave valuable advice on the interpretation of electrophysiological
949 data. MI checked the annotations of electrophysiological data and supervised this work, providing it
950 with a clinical perspective. MB provided valuable advice on electrophysiological modeling issues,
951 participated in the critical discussion of the results and contributed to the writing of the manuscript. All
952 authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

953

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964

965 **8 Conflict of interest statement**

966 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
967 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

968 **9 Nomenclature**

2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
AP	Action potential
APD	Action potential duration
BCL	Basic cycle length
SCC	Slow conducting channel
DE-MRI	Delayed enhancement-MRI
EAM	Electroanatomical map/mapping
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EGM	Electrogram
FEM	Finite-element method
LAT	Local activation time
LV	Left ventricle
MI	Myocardial infarction
RFA	Radiofrequency ablation
RV	Right ventricle
SD	Standard deviation
VT	Ventricular tachycardia
DTI	Diffusion tensor imaging
EP	Electrophysiology/electrophysiological
ER	Electrical remodeling

969

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- 1526

1527 **Tables**

1528 **Table 1.** Different versions of the computational model of ventricles according to the kind of
 1529 remodeling included in the BZ (ER and/or fibrosis) and results of *in-silico* VT inducibility tests
 1530 performed with CVs in BZ reduced by 75% with respect to the healthy tissue. In the cases of positive
 1531 VT induction, we specify the premature stimulus (S2 or S3) responsible for the unidirectional block
 1532 triggering the reentrant VT and its CI, as well as the BCL and heart rate associated with the VT.

Model version	Fibrosis in BZ	ER in BZ	Pacing Site		
			<i>endo#1</i>	<i>epi#1</i>	<i>epi#2</i>
#1	0%	NO	no VT	no VT	no VT
#2	10%		no VT	no VT	no VT
#3	20%		no VT	no VT	no VT
#4	30%		no VT	S3 – 290 ms 510 ms – 117 bpm	no VT
#5	0%	YES	no VT	S2 – 360 ms 506 ms – 118 bpm	no VT
#6	10%		S3 – 370 ms 526 ms – 114 bpm	S2 – 360 ms 526 ms – 114 bpm	no VT
#7	20%		S3 – 370 ms 520 ms – 115 bpm	S2 – 360 ms 520 ms – 115 bpm	no VT
#8	30%		no VT	no VT	no VT

1533

1534 **Figures**

1535 **Figure 1.** (A) Manual segmentation process of cardiac DE-MRI performed with Seg3D, displaying
 1536 three slices corresponding to the standard cardiac planes: short-axis (*left*), four-chamber plane (*center*)
 1537 and long-axis showing the LV (*right*). (Note that in those views the LV appears on the right side and
 1538 the RV on the left). Contours highlighted in distinct colors show: LV myocardium including the septum
 1539 (*red*), RV myocardium (*blue*) and papillary muscles and endocardial trabeculations of LV (*yellow*) and
 1540 RV (*green*). (B) Posterior view of a coronal cross-section (four-chamber plane) of the hexahedra-based
 1541 FEM volume mesh of the 3D *patient-specific* ventricular model. Various cardiac regions are labeled
 1542 with different colors: septum (*blue*), LV free wall (*cyan*), RV free wall (*green*) and papillary muscles
 1543 and main endocardial trabeculations of LV (*yellow*) and RV (*red*). (C) Transmural heterogeneity of
 1544 ventricular myocardium, showing the distribution of the three different kinds of ventricular myocytes:
 1545 endo-, mid- (M cells) and epicardial cells. (D) Left antero-lateral view of the 3D ventricular model
 1546 displaying a representation of cardiac fibers orientation at different wall depths (endocardium, mid-
 1547 myocardium and epicardium).

1548

1549 **Figure 2.** (A) Segmentation process from short-axis DE-MRI slices of the heterogeneous remodeling
 1550 caused by MI, including infarct scar and BZ. Left panel shows the first step that involves the manual
 1551 delineation of remote ROI (region-of-interest) (*green*) and infarcted ROI (*yellow*) within the LV
 1552 myocardium ROI (*red*), also displaying the RV myocardium ROI (*cyan*). Right panel shows the
 1553 segmentation for infarct scar (*purple*) and BZ (*yellow*) resulting from the application within the
 1554 infarcted ROI of thresholds determined by SD method from the remote ROI of each slice. (B) 3D
 1555 representation of the MI reconstructed from DE-MRI images, showing posterior views of the 3D
 1556 surface model of ventricles (rendered with transparency) along with those hexahedral elements of
 1557 volume mesh labeled as infarct scar (*red*) and BZ (*blue*).

1558

1559 **Figure 3.** (A) Grey intensity levels from DE-MRI mapped into the hexahedral volume mesh of the 3D
 1560 ventricular model, showing a postero-basal view of the whole model (*left*) and a basal view of a cross-
 1561 section in the short-axis plane (*right*). The next three panels show the 3D fibrosis distribution resulting
 1562 from the introduction of several degrees of structural remodeling within the BZ: (B) 10%, (C) 20% and
 1563 (D) 30% patchy fibrosis. All those panels show a posterior view of the 3D surface model of ventricles
 1564 (rendered with transparency) together with those hexahedral elements labelled as BZ (*blue*) and fibrosis
 1565 (*orange*) extracted from the volume mesh of ventricular model. In each panel there is an image showing
 1566 both the BZ and fibrosis (*left*) and another one only displaying the fibrotic elements (*right*).

1567

1568 **Figure 4.** Registration process between CARTO surface meshes and the 3D ventricular model. (A)
 1569 Two posterior views of the 3D surface model of ventricles rendered with transparency, showing
 1570 registered CARTO surfaces for both endocardia (*left*) and epicardium (*right*). (B) CARTO
 1571 measurement points projected onto the 3D model with colored spheres representing CARTO points
 1572 recorded from LV endocardium (*red*), RV endocardium (*blue*) and epicardium (*green*). (C) Postero-
 1573 lateral view of the 3D ventricular model showing a possible epicardial SCC mainly composed of BZ
 1574 (*blue*) intermingled with some thin patches of healthy tissue at epicardial level (*beige*) and completely
 1575 surrounded by infarct scar (*red*), closely matching the location of projected CARTO points tagged

1576 during the RFA procedure as candidates to be part of a SCC (*green spheres*) according to the features
 1577 of their EGMs.

1578

1579 **Figure 5.** 3D Torso model. (A) Anterior view of the torso model, showing the 3D surfaces that
 1580 represents all organs and tissues included (bones, lungs, liver, ventricles, atria and blood pools of four
 1581 cardiac chambers). Blue spheres represent the location of virtual electrodes corresponding to precordial
 1582 leads for ECG computation, placed in its standard positions. (B) Coronal cross-section of volume mesh
 1583 of the 3D torso model, showing the edges of tetrahedral elements that are highly refined in the region
 1584 of ventricles. (C) Labeled volume mesh. Different colors indicate to which organ or anatomical
 1585 structure each tetrahedral element belongs as a result of the labelling process of volume mesh: lungs
 1586 (*orange*), bones (*yellow*), liver (*purple*) and ventricles (*red*).

1587

1588 **Figure 6.** Comparison between APs generated by the original version of ten Tusscher model (ten
 1589 Tusscher and Panfilov, 2006), used in our simulations for healthy myocardium, and APs resulting from
 1590 our modified version of such model for the remodeled BZ. Left column shows APs from a simulation
 1591 with a single isolated cell, after stabilizing the model at a BCL of 800 ms, while right column displays
 1592 APs obtained for a cell embedded in a 3D tissue (i.e., surrounded by other cells and electrically coupled
 1593 to them) exclusively composed of remodeled myocytes.

1594

1595 **Figure 7.** Activation map for CARTO-derived sinus activation, corresponding to the sixth heartbeat
 1596 simulated with the ventricular model with ER and 10% fibrosis in BZ (model #6). Top row shows an
 1597 anterior (A) and a posterior (B) view of a coronal cross-section (four-chamber plane) of the ventricular
 1598 model, showing the activation on the endocardial surfaces. Bottom row also displays anterior (C) and
 1599 posterior (D) views of the whole model, showing the activation at epicardial level. Black regions
 1600 correspond to not activated tissue (not depolarized) due to fibrosis accumulation. Grey region
 1601 represents the infarct scar, modeled as non-conducting tissue.

1602

1603 **Figure 8.** APD maps showing the epicardial surface of the posterior wall of the ventricular model,
 1604 exhibiting the differences in repolarization patterns during simulated sinus rhythm for the four versions
 1605 of the model resulting from the combination of absence and presence of ER with no fibrosis and with
 1606 10% image-based patchy fibrosis in the BZ. Those maps correspond to the sixth heartbeat simulated
 1607 from the CARTO-derived activation pattern at a BCL of 800 ms (75 bpm). As observed, both the ER
 1608 and the presence of patchy fibrosis in the BZ affects the APDs in the BZ, creating repolarization
 1609 dispersion around the infarct scar. (See Supplementary Material for APD maps with 20% and 30%
 1610 fibrosis in the BZ).

1611

1612 **Figure 9.** Comparison between real and simulated ECG signals recorded at precordial leads in sinus
 1613 rhythm. These plots display the ECG simulated with all model versions including ER (models #5-8),
 1614 combined with the four tested levels of image-based patchy fibrosis in the BZ. The ECG for the model
 1615 version with ER, 10% fibrosis and the CVs reduced by 50% in BZ (10% fib*), instead of 75%, is also

1616 represented. Correlation coefficients (CORR) are included in the plots legend. Those signals were
 1617 obtained by propagating through the 3D torso model the sixth heartbeat simulated from the CARTO-
 1618 derived sinus activation pattern at a BCL of 800 ms (75 bpm). (See Supplementary Material for
 1619 simulated ECGs with model versions without ER in the BZ).

1620

1621 **Figure 10.** Pacing sites for the application of PES protocols aiming to test VT inducibility by
 1622 computational simulation. The dark grey region represents the infarct scar.

1623

1624 **Figure 11.** Reentrant monomorphic VT induced *in-silico* by PES protocol. Posterior views of the 3D
 1625 ventricular model displaying potential maps at different time instants of the PES protocol from pacing
 1626 site *epi#1* leading to positive VT induction on the model #6 (ER and 10% fibrosis in BZ). Non-excitable
 1627 scar is represented in gray color. White arrows indicate direction of the depolarization wavefront. (A)
 1628 Only one premature stimulus (S2) was delivered at a CI of 360 ms. (B) The wavefront generated by S2
 1629 stimulus causes a functional propagation block at the lower side of the epicardial isthmus (see white
 1630 circle). (C) The wavefront continues propagating around the infarct scar, but not through the epicardial
 1631 isthmus due to the functional block caused by S2 stimulus. (D) The wavefront reaches the upper side
 1632 of the epicardial isthmus after propagating all around the infarct scar. (E) The wavefront enters through
 1633 the upper side of the epicardial isthmus, propagating across the channel until leaving it through its
 1634 lower side (unidirectional block) to propagate again around the scar, giving rise to a reentrant activity
 1635 leading to a self-sustained monomorphic VT. (F) Activation map of a cycle of the induced VT,
 1636 confirming that the epicardial isthmus constitutes a SCC acting as structural substrate for this infarct-
 1637 related VT.

1638

1639 **Figure 12.** APD maps resulting from the propagation of the last stimulus of the S1 phase triggered
 1640 from pacing point *epi#1*. These maps correspond to three out of the four different versions of the
 1641 ventricular model that enabled positive VT induction in *in-silico* tests. All of them show repolarization
 1642 dispersion in the BZ surrounding the infarct scar, with a region of longer APDs at both ends of the
 1643 epicardial SCC, especially at the lower side where the unidirectional propagation block that triggers
 1644 the reentrant activity occurs. Black regions correspond to not activated tissue due to fibrosis
 1645 accumulation.

1646

1647 **Figure 13.** ECGs during clinical VT. Comparison between real (*black*) and simulated ECGs with
 1648 different model versions for *in-silico* induced VT. Simulated ECGs correspond to all model versions
 1649 that enabled a positive VT induction: models #4 (*orange*), #5 (*blue*), #6 (*green*) and #7 (*magenta*). The
 1650 ECG for model #6 (ER and 10% fibrosis in BZ) with the CVs reduced by 50% (instead of 75%) is also
 1651 represented (*cyan*). Together with the patient's ECG (*black*), a resampled version of the ECG obtained
 1652 with model #6 and CVs reduced by 75% in BZ is displayed (*red*) to ease a visual comparison of the
 1653 waveform of both signals.